

Criteria list for synthesizing insights gained on the impact chain methodology and for adaptation decision making

Work Package 5 - Deliverable D5.1.

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Introduction

The overall aim of WP5[6]¹ is to synthesize and consolidate findings and methods gained in the UNCHAIN project, i.e. in the previous WPs. It brings together the insights gained in the case studies to develop a consolidated validation method (with a focus on impact chains (IC) and science-user interface) and identify opportunities for changes in adaptation decision making in Europe and beyond. Furthermore, it reflects on the process of stakeholder engagement and knowledge co-production to bridge the gap between climate science, policy and practice, and how related strategies could be improved.

Specifically, this deliverable sets the basis for the validation and synthesis process to be carried out in WP5, with the aim to develop the following deliverables:

- D5[6].2 - Improved and adapted impact chain method (Guidebook and reflection on insights and lessons learnt) [as journal article and public report]
- D5[6].3. - Recommendations for improved adaptation decision making and policy [as policy brief]

Therefore, this deliverable serves internal purposes to guide the validation process. It has been developed at an early-stage of WP5 to allow its uptake already during the case study research activities and its possible continuous update and evolution during the remaining months of UNCHAIN.

Scope and purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable has been developed under ‘Task 5[6].1. Develop criteria for validation of case study results for (i) the development and consolidation of methods and (ii) strategies for adaptation policies with stakeholder involvement’ under the lead of partner PLUS, in collaboration with SEI, IEO, FhG, TEC and INSA.

As outlined above, the scope and purpose of this deliverable is:

- To define validation criteria which are able to guide the process in WP5 to achieve its deliverables (as mentioned above)
- The criteria are meant as a toolset to compile the adoption of the impact chain method in the subsequent tasks of WP5
- To provide guidance for case studies to identify and develop criteria for validation of results

The integration of the related WP4 and this deliverable is shown in Fig.1. Starting from the results and insights gained in the different case studies, WP4 aims to evaluate the results, based on research questions identified as well as the main innovations of UNCHAIN. An important prerequisite - for the work in WP5 - are the findings from WP4. Therefore, in preparation for this deliverable a joint coordination with the leaders of relevant tasks in WP4 was carried out, and especially the approach outlined in deliverable 4.1. on ‘Case(s) Studies Evaluation Framework’ was synchronised with the approach presented in this deliverable. While WP4 is an open evaluation in regard to all research questions and innovations of UNCHAIN (see tables 3.1-3.4 in Del. 4.1), WP5 validates the findings to decide what is being taken up in the improved and adapted IC method (Del. 5[6].2) as well as for the recommendations (Del. 5[6].3). Importantly, WP5 focuses solely on the innovations related to the IC

¹ WP5 according to the adapted work plan; WP6 as initially mentioned in the proposal

model and the co-production of knowledge (see tables 3.1 and 3.2. in Del. 4.1). For this purpose, a validation framework was developed, which is outlined in the following.

Figure 1: ‘Distillation process’ in UNCHAIN; from case study results, its validation towards an updated IC methodology and policy recommendations

Evaluation Criteria and Process

Concept and Background on Validation

As outlined by Zebisch et al. (2021) the ‘Vulnerability Sourcebook’ (Fritzsche et al. 2015) was developed to address the need for an operational vulnerability and risk assessment that allows for comparison in time and/or space, and which also supports monitoring and evaluation purposes. The Vulnerability Sourcebook - with its supplement (Zebisch et al. 2017) and adaptations (Hagenlocher et al. 2018) - is a standardised methodological framework for climate change vulnerability assessments. This framework is applicable to vulnerability and risk assessments from national to local scale. It follows the full planning cycle of the adaptation policy cycle process, from identification of the adaptation demand and selection of measures, to the monitoring and evaluation of the progress of adaptation interventions in lowering vulnerability (Zebisch et al. 2021). The sourcebook is structured in eight concrete steps, to develop – based on quantitative as well as partly qualitative methods – the risk/vulnerability assessment building by producing outputs/‘products’ such as impact chains, maps together with narratives/reports. Impact chains are conceptual models describing climate impact as cause-effect relationships within a socio-ecological system and are the major approach for operationalising vulnerability/risk in the context of the sourcebook.

Next to the conceptual design, the assessment of the output quality, as well as the match outputs (and if relevant the process) with specific user needs, should be an essential activity accompanying such assessments. According to O’Keefe et al. (1987), validation means “to build the right system”, whereas

verification means “to build a system right”. At a first glance, the difference seems to be little, but in fact it is crucial as it defines validation as a mandatory step within a production workflow that builds on user requirements (D’Oleire-Oltmanns et al. 2015). In other words, beyond answering the question “Are we doing the right thing right?” validation is required to answer first the question “Are we doing the right thing?” (Zeil & Lang 2009). Consequently, these two guiding questions should be considered in a user-oriented *validation* process, which is at the main purpose of WP5.

In the context of UNCHAIN, it is therefore planned to validate main research findings, which derive from the case studies and their evaluation in WP4. The purpose for this validation is to provide thresholds and criteria for the different methods/toolsets applied, if they are ‘fit for the purpose’ of being integrated for the ‘improved and adapted impact chain methodology’.

Therefore, we have chosen to use the following validation questions to guide the distillation process in WP5 considering the case study evaluation deriving from WP4 (based on Zeil & Lang 2009, D’Oleire-Oltmanns et al. 2015):

- (i) Are we doing the right thing? - i.e., does the method provide results which are relevant to the user?
- (ii) Are we doing the right thing right? - i.e., is the method/product/result sound, effective, robust, etc.)?

According to Zeil & Lang (2009), the first guiding question (i) can be understood as the ‘user validation’, whereas the second question (ii) addresses the technical/scientific validation. Therefore, following this approach, the benefit is that we can address both – the user perspective as well as the ‘science’ perspective together. Zeil & Lang (2009) built on elements of the Logical Framework Analysis (LFA) (e.g., Cordingley 1995) to populate the questions with criteria, which was further developed by D’Oleire-Oltmanns et al. (2015) for map products in the context of the Copernicus Security Service.

In the following, we present our choice of validation criteria for both topics relevant for WP5[6] and their attribution to the use of climate information. This comprises the technical validation domain, including a question defining a threshold criterion for the possible uptake into the adapted method (D5[6].2.) as well as for the recommendations to be identified (D5[6].3.). An overview is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Overview of validation criteria as well as the step-wise approach, guiding the validation process

Criteria for ‘impact chain model and uncertainties’

As pointed out above, the focus of this validation addresses specifically the impact chain model methodology, leading to the deliverable on the ‘improved and adapted impact chain methodology’. This will be built on the research questions, the associated modules and results from the evaluation in WP4 (see also Fig. 2). The following are the key criteria to be validated (see Tab. 1) that are accompanied by a requirement (see Tab.1 and Tab.2 below), which needs to be fulfilled to be considered in the revised methodology:

- **Relevance** refers to the extent to which the method/tool responds to the users’ needs/policies/priorities in the context of climate risk management (modified after OECD 2019)
- **Applicability** is understood as the usefulness of the method/tool, the quality of being appropriate in practice and its availability to users
- **Comprehensibility** is understood as the quality of being easy or possible to be applied and understood by other experts, with the requirement that a documentation of the methodology/tool is available
- **Scientific Validity** refers to how well the method/tool has undergone a scientific test or piece of research, and how well it actually assesses what it sets out to, or how well it reflects the reality it claims to represent (after AQR²) - for our purpose in UNCHAIN, reflecting climate risk and its related components
- **Effectiveness** refers to the extent to which the method/tool achieved, or is expected to achieve, its objectives and its results (modified after OECD 2019)
- **Transferability** refers to the degree to which the method/tool can be generalized or transferred to other contexts or settings
- **Scalability** refers to the degree to which the method/tool can be extended in size (e.g., number of assessment units) or scale.

The criteria have been identified based on a literature review and a joint workshop with the involved researchers of this WP. An initial, longer list of criteria was reduced based on a scoring exercise with the researchers and then finalised by the authors of this deliverable.

Table 1: Validation components, their criteria and associated requirements for validating the methods related to the ‘impact chain model and uncertainties’ (building on Del. 4.1.; table 3.1.)

Validation component	Criteria	Requirement
Are we doing the right thing?	Relevance	Supports the identification of climate risks with the option to identify climate change adaptation measures - based on impact chains - with the aim to derive a quantitative and qualitative (or both combined) climate risk assessment
	Applicability	The method is generic in its application as well as not limited to exclusive/commercial toolsets
	Comprehensibility	The method is documented and guidance is provided

² <https://www.agr.org.uk/glossary/validity>

Are we doing the right thing right?	Scientific Validity	The approach is scientifically valid (and reproducible) and has undergone a review (e.g., by another expert round, review etc.)
		The impact chains are based on a diverse set of stakeholder knowledge together with scientific findings
	Effectiveness	The method can be implemented without primary data collection (i.e., it can built on existing datasets)
		The method allows the integration of data from heterogenous data sources (quantitative, qualitative, expert, stakeholder...)
		It can be implemented within a feasible timeframe and practicable team size
		It involves stakeholders in all its main phases
	Transferability	The method can be transferred to other application/sector contexts
		It can be transferred to other geographical settings
	Scalability	The method can be applied at different geographical scales (local, provincial, national, regional...)
		It can be scaled across varying numbers of assessment units (e.g., 3-4 admin units vs. 15-20 admin units)

Criteria for ‘co-production of knowledge’

As described in previous WP1-3 reports, for the purpose of our case study implementation and analysis we operationalise the UNCHAIN research Innovation of User Interface and Stakeholder Interactions by adopting a more specific, pluralistic, and empirically grounded participatory research method. Accordingly, we interpret this innovation in terms of a user and stakeholder-centric, process-oriented and demand-driven approach, commonly referred to as ‘co-production of knowledge’. We start from the following working definition of knowledge co-production by Norström et al (2019): “an iterative and collaborative process involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future.”

Based on the evaluation framework (D.4.1), we focus in particular on the following two research questions:

- How does knowledge co-production in climate risk assessments inform decision-making and adaptation action?
- What are the benefits of adopting an integrated approach combining knowledge co-production and impact modelling?

To identify criteria for how the method of knowledge co-production contributes to improved adaptation decision-making and influences policy outcomes we start from four guiding principles

proposed by Norström et al. (2020, p. 3). These principles are developed to support knowledge co-production processes and their evaluation including aspects such as quality and success:

- **Context-based:** Situate the process in a particular context, place, or issue.
- **Pluralistic:** Explicitly recognize the multiple ways of knowing and doing.
- **Goal-oriented:** Articulate clearly defined, shared and meaningful goals that are related to the challenge at hand.
- **Interactive:** Allow for ongoing learning among actors, active engagement and frequent interactions

Of importance to our criteria are also the three goals of the Tandem framework (Daniels et al., 2020, p. 1):

- To improve the ways in which all participants *work together* to purposefully design *transdisciplinary knowledge integration processes* (co-exploration and co-production processes that bring together different knowledge types across the science-society interface).
- To co-explore decision-relevant needs for the co-production of *integrated climate information* (i.e., decision-relevant climate and non-climate information); and
- To increase individual and institutional capacities, collaboration, communication, and networks that can translate this information into climate-resilient decision-making and action.

Table 2: Validation components, their criteria and associated requirements for validating the methods related for the ‘co-production of knowledge’. Note that the two criteria transferability and scalability have been omitted in the table considering their limited relevance for the knowledge co-production approach (building on Del. 4.1.; table 3.2).

Validation component	Criteria	Requirement
Are we doing the right thing?	Relevance	Outputs and outcomes address stakeholders’ and societal needs and expectations.
		Stakeholders perceive the science products as relevant for achieving/having led to (or potentially leading to) more accurate, informed decisions, planning and policy processes.
		The co-production process contributes to improved decision-making and policy (e.g., agendas, capacities and decisions) that respond to goals co-defined by stakeholders and researchers.
	Applicability	The method is flexible, iterative and sensitive to decision-contexts.
	Comprehensibility	Expert groups to depart from and learn from existing practices and guidances available online and in the literature.
		Make use of professional facilitator and/or knowledge broker in the co-production process.
	Scientific Validity	Starts from state-of-the-art and has undergone a peer review process

Are we doing the right thing right?		Validity and reliability have been tested and secured on a cross-case study basis
	<i>Effectiveness</i>	The impact chains are based on a diverse set of stakeholder knowledge together with scientific findings
		Science-user interactions and co-production leads to demonstrated outcomes, e.g. building trust, new insights, mutual understanding, relationships, and social networks.

Proposed process

Overall, the approach is being built on the

- research questions as identified in the case study protocol, chapter ‘Research innovation relating to Impact Chain method’ and Table 1 (D2.1, page 21ff); and
- the evaluation framework of the case studies developed in WP4 (D4.1. on ‘Case(s) Studies Evaluation Framework’)

Therefore, we aim to allow a continuous flow of information and especially distillation of insights as outlined above.

We propose the following steps to implement the proposed validation concept (see also Fig. 2 for a simplified version):

- **Step 0:** The proposed workflow is communicated – once the deliverable is finalised – to the case study leaders for transparency and consideration during the case study research phase.
- **Step 1:** Once the evaluation results from WP4 are available the criteria from above are used to validate the results – especially for the IC method. This should also be linked to the modules of the sourcebook. If clarifications are needed, there will be a direct follow-up with the cases (task 5[6].2, task 5[6].4 as in the Description of Work).
- **Step 2:** After the review of the evaluation, a joint workshop with the project team is carried out to review and finalise the findings (task 5[6].2, task 5[6].4).
- **Step 3:** Documentation and consolidation of the method for impact chains and recommendations in the core team of WP5 (task 5[6].3, task 5[6].5). Finalise overall insights (task 5[6].6) during a joint workshop with the project team.

Conclusions

This deliverable sets out the way ahead to consolidate research findings in UNCHAIN. It has been developed at a relative early stage of the project and as the start of WP5. This provides the opportunity that the proposed approach is continuously monitored and adapted, if there is a need to as a living document.

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